

Future research themes for the hospitality sector: A bibliometric analysis

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Abstract

This research presents a bibliometric analysis of 837 publications on hospitality sector (specifically on hotels and restaurants) between 2010 and 2023, crossing the main research topics with the implemented methodology. The data used for the analysis were obtained from the Web of Science (WoS). This analysis has been developed considering three periods: precovid, covid, and post-covid. Strategic diagrams and cluster graphics were obtained with the SciMAT program. The hospitality sector is one of the most affected by the pandemic situation and it is crucial not only to know the lines already targeted by the academics to raise clarity and new business models, but the methodologies applied to tackle the diverse issues under research. The reason behind this analyses is the consideration that only with a thorough and innovative vision and research of the varied challenges in the sector new ideas can come up to provide solutions. The pre-covid period features 209 keywords, of which 80% are repeated in the covid period. The covid period studied, features 192 keywords, with 77% continuing to be of importance in the post-covid period. The results reveal that the main topics under consideration are: “behavior”, “consumers”, “business big data”, “consumer preferences”, “marketing”, “perceived value”, “CSR”, “local food”, “over tourism”, and “SDG”, missing a deeper understanding of “sustainable communication”, “environmental marketing strategy”, “green spaces” and “consumer preferences”. On the other hand, the most applied theories are Behavior and Social Exchange theories. In terms of methodologies, logit models are very extended as well as structural equation models and clusters analyses, but there is lack of application of data mining, neuromarketing and co-word analysis, which could increase the knowledge through a new technology and methodology approach.

Key words: Hospitality Sector, Bibliometric Analysis, Sustainability, Covid-19

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